

FAIR terminology meets CLEAR Global

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Abstract. This paper presents the design and implementation of a web application aimed at facilitating access to a multilingual terminology database specifically created for speakers of marginalized languages that often cannot access information they need and want in a language and format they understand. The database contains essential concepts translated into 39 languages, for a total of 9,506 terms. The design of the database and the web application has been performed in order to follow the FAIR principle of Open Science in order to guarantee efficient data organization and retrieval. The web application, developed using the R Shiny framework, enables users to search the database by selecting a source language and, optionally, a target language. The interface displays concept definitions in English and provides filtered lists of equivalents in the chosen languages. Users can export selected datasets in TermBase eXchange standard (TBX) format for reusability. The interface offers a user-friendly experience, allowing users to navigate through the database effortlessly.

Keywords: language technology in crisis situations · humanitarian termbases · FAIR terminology

1 Introduction

The ability to access vital information across languages is fundamental for effective communication and understanding in an interconnected world and even more in situations where the possible miscommunication in critical situations can worsen the severity of the event and retard effective response efforts. For example, during a crisis, there is often a flood of information from various sources, including official channels, social media, and person-to-person. Sorting through this abundance of information can be overwhelming for both responders and affected individuals, leading to confusion and conflicting messages. Crisis response efforts involve multiple organizations, agencies, and stakeholders operating in

dynamic and high-pressure environments. In multicultural societies or international crises, language and cultural differences can delay and interfere effective communication between communities. Misinterpretation of messages, inability to understand instructions, and cultural sensitivities may hinder the dissemination of critical information and the provision of assistance. Finally, infrastructure damage or overload of communication networks during crises can disrupt traditional communication channels, such as phone lines or internet access. This can limit the ability of responders to disseminate information and for affected individuals to seek help or access emergency services. Addressing these challenges requires proactive measures, including robust communication strategies, interoperable communication systems, and linguistically sensitive messaging.

Terminology databases play a crucial role in this context as a step to overcome linguistic barriers by providing comprehensive collections of essential concepts and their designations in different languages. This paper presents the design and implementation of a web application aimed at facilitating access to a multilingual terminology database, catering to diverse linguistic needs. The term base was originally developed by CLEAR Global in collaboration with its partners, and over the years it was translated into more and more languages.⁵

The foundation of our research lies in the creation of a structured database adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and ISO standards, ensuring efficient organization and retrieval of multilingual terminological data.

1.1 Background

Translators without Borders (TWB/CLEAR Global) is a prominent organization in the translation sector, positioning itself as a charity while operating with a corporate structure. TWB is a part of CLEAR Global, a US-based nonprofit and operates on an asset-centered, platform-based model, primarily led by major industry players, but also partnering with small local NGO's. Its mission is to help people get vital information and be heard, whatever language they speak. The objectives of TWB include facilitating volunteer translation services on a large scale and leveraging technology to streamline translation efforts [2]. By mobilizing over 100,000 volunteers and utilizing a platform-based model, the organization provides language services and solutions, helping partner organizations improve communication with marginalized communities, particularly in crisis situations and humanitarian contexts.⁶

The discussion presented in [4] emphasizes the vital role of language in the well-being and safety of refugees, specifically Ukrainian refugees. It stresses the importance of tailored communication to meet language preferences and sensitivities, necessitating data on language preferences. It also recommends basic staff training and collaboration with language service providers to enhance communication and information access for refugees, underlining the significance of

⁵ <https://clearglobal.org/safeguarding-and-psea/>

⁶ <https://clearglobal.org/mt-rwanda-pushing-forward-language-tech-in-kinyarwanda/>

language support in crisis situations for ensuring effective support delivery and refugee integration.

A similar problem has been presented by [5] where the authors propose a Participatory Design approach used to investigate technology’s potential benefits for refugees in Malaysia. This work emphasizes the need for mobile applications to prioritize aspects like privacy, safety, social connections, skill development, and language translation for their digital empowerment and facilitate their integration and well-being in new environments.

However, as shown in [12], it is estimated that over 90% of the world’s languages lack adequate language technology support, affecting billions of people. These ‘low-resource languages’ in computer science, suffer from a scarcity of training text required for machine translation models. This imbalance in language technology amplifies the dominance of already well-supported languages.

[1] discuss existing models for student translation volunteering due to ethical concerns with for-profit initiatives and limitations of non-profit organizations, which restrict participation to trained translators. The authors propose Action Translate, a platform enabling student volunteering by utilizing machine translation for a streamlined experience. Recommendations include a volunteer-centric approach focusing on the agency, accountability, and collaboration to create sustainable platforms leveraging students’ multilingual skills and motivations.

The question of how to realize these language resources in a sustainable way is proposed by [7]. In this work, the author proposes to develop machine translation (MT) systems for low-resource languages and he emphasizes the ecological and social impacts of mainstream MT systems developed by large corporations, advocating for alternatives, independently operated "low-tech" MT solutions. Aligning with indigenous values, sustainable MT workflows prioritize inclusivity, collaboration, and environmental stewardship, promoting the preservation and promotion of indigenous languages and knowledge.

2 Description of Original Dataset

CLEAR Global developed the PSEA (protection from sexual exploitation and abuse) and safeguarding glossary with international organizations such as the International Organization for Migration, the Safeguarding Resource and Support Hub, the CDAC network, CHS Alliance, UNICEF, and other members of the Inter-Agency Standing Committee. The 208 concepts and their English definitions were selected and agreed upon by the representatives of these organizations in 2021. The first target languages to be included in the glossary were also requested and funded by these organization. Subsequent expansion into new target languages has been necessitated by crises happening around the world. The floods in Pakistan prompted 5 new languages, the war in Ukraine brought about the addition of 10 Eastern European languages, the earthquake in Turkey made Turkish necessary (as Arabic and Kurdish languages were already included).⁷ PSEA is a sensitive topic, which is made even more complicated by

⁷ For a detailed history, see <https://clearglobal.org/safeguarding-and-psea/>

Sectors	English	Amharic	Arabic	Armenian	Azerbaijani	Balochi	Bengali	Czech	
(3) Forms of harm and abuse	abuse	ጥቃት	اعتداء	պարսպարում	zorakılıq	عبر ارتى	অপব্যৱহাৰ	zneužívání	abus
(2)	accountability	ተጠያቂነት	مسئلة	պատասխանատվություն	cavabdehlik	مسار زوك	অৱদায়বিত্ত	odpovědnost	respoi
(2)	action plan	የኢርጋት ግብር- ገብር	خطة عمل	գործողությունների ծրագիր	tacbirler planı	اھل ۛ شون	অর্ক বরিব্রুত	akční plán	plan d
(2) People, individuals	affected population	ተጋዳ የህዝብ ከፍሎች	السكان المتضررين	տուժած քնակընդուն	zarar çakmiş əhali	سھیلگیك اھالی	অভিভোগ অৱস্থা	postížené obyvatelstvo	populí affect
(2) People, individuals	associated personnel	ተዛግጭኞች ያለቶው ሰዎች ነ	المتخاضمون الصلة	կիցընդակած անձնակազմ	aidyyani gəxslər	سھلگیك کارکنوك	অৱস্থা অৱস্থা স্বীকৃত	přidružený personál	perso assoc

Fig. 2. A screenshot of the original Web application running at CLEAR Global

columns that can be scrolled horizontally. Additional information on the term (definition, source, usage note, etc.) can be seen by clicking on the term. One important element that is added to this application is the possibility to listen to the pronunciation of the term for some languages (for example, in Figure 2 Amharic, Arabic, Bengali, and Czech have this feature active).

3 Designing the Database

In order to reshape the dataset and design a database that follows the FAIR terminology paradigm [11,9,8], we re-engineered the abstract structure of a possible database that represents these data according to the ISO 16642: 2017 [6]. This standard specifies a concept oriented three-tier hierarchical structure for a terminology database, where the three levels are: Concept Entry which is “information that pertains to a single concept”, Language Section which is a “container for all the term sections of a concept entry for a given language, as well as information pertaining to the concept in that language”, and Term Section which “contains exactly one term, and information about the term”.

We use the entity-relationship (ER) model [3] to design the abstract representation of the terminology database that, in this project, will be subsequently transformed into a relational database. The basic elements of this schema include: entities, which represent the set of objects of interest that have common properties; properties, which describe the attributes or characteristics of these entities; relationships, which delineate a logical link among entities with a corresponding pair of numbers (the cardinality (n, m)) that indicate the minimum and maximum number of elements that can be involved in this relationship.

The Entity-Relationship (ER) schema in Figure 3 can be read as follows:

- The entity “Concept Entry” is identified by the related “Concept” through the relationship ‘hasConcept’, with cardinality (1, 1). A concept entry contains one or more language sections (cardinality (1, n)).

Fig. 3. The ER schema of the terminology database.

- The entity “Language Section” is identified by the pair “Concept Entry” and “Language” through the relationships ‘contain’ and ‘hasLanguage’. A language section is associated with the “Term Section” entity and can include different term sections.
- The entity “Term Section” is identified by the “Term” itself through the association ‘hasTerm’ and can be included in only one “Language Section”.
- The entity “Concept” is identified by its own Identifier and must be associated with only one “Concept Entry”.
- The entity “Language” identified by the name that is used in the original dataset and it is associated to the corresponding “Language Section”.
- The entity “Term” is identified by its own Identifier and must be associated with only one Term Section.

4 Implementing a Web Application

The design of the Web Application has followed two main principles: i) to allow users to search the multilingual terminology database with a source language and an optional target language; ii) to allow reusability of the database by means of standard serialization of the data into the TermBase eXchange standard (TBX). In particular, the application has been designed and implemented extending the R Shiny framework for web interactivity proposed by [10]. Compared to the previous solution, our application includes the datatable (DT) package¹⁰

¹⁰ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/data.table/>

CLEAR Global FAIR termbase

Source language: French | term: auteur d'une infraction

Target language: German

English definition: A person who is thought to have caused harm or acted against the organization's code of conduct.

Download TBX

Source Table

Concept ID	Language	Definition	Term ID	Term	Region	Term type	Head term
35	French	Personne accusée d'avoir causé un préjudice ou enfreint le code de conduite de l'organisation.	35-12	auteur d'une infraction			True
35	French		35-14	auteur du méfait			
35	French		35-13	auteur du fait illicite			

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries

Target Table

Concept ID	Language	Definition	Term ID	Term	Region	Term type	Head term
35	German	Eine Person, von der angenommen wird, dass sie Schaden verursacht oder gegen den Verhaltenskodex der Organisation verstoßen hat.	35-41	Schädiger			True
35	German		35-15	Schädigerin			

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries

Fig. 4. Screenshot of the current Web application to browse and download the terminology database.

to review the annotation, and the textplot package¹¹ for text visualization and analysis.

The current interface of the Web application¹² is shown in Figure 4. A sequence of steps to interact with the interface is the following:

1. The user selects the source language and the term to analyze.
2. The interface displays the English definition of the concept designated by the chosen term.
3. The interface displays all the equivalents for that term in the chosen source language. The user can perform an additional filter of the displayed rows by using the "search" box.
4. The user can choose a target language for the chosen term.
5. The interface displays all the equivalents for that term in the chosen target language. The user can perform an additional filter of the displayed rows by using the "search" box.
6. The user can export the selected dataset as a TBX file.

Besides the organization of the visualization from a different perspective compared to the original application, an optional bilingual terminological view compared to a fully multilingual parallel comparison, we want to highlight once more the importance of the organization of the data using international standards, like TBX. This feature will allow the possibility to broaden the interoperability and the reusability of the data produced as well as the compatibility with various lan-

¹¹ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/textplot/>

¹² https://shiny.dei.unipd.it/CLEARGlobal_FAIR_psea

guage technologies and terminological tools, facilitating integration with other systems and organizations, such as the IATE terminology management system.¹³

Finally, we have already planned to release the open source code of the application as well as the full data (that will be in any case downloadable by the application).

5 Final Remarks and Future Works

This research presents a step towards facilitating access to vital information across languages through the development of a multilingual terminology database that supports the FAIR principles and is compliant with ISO standards as well as a user-friendly web application. Through the implementation of the application, users can easily search, browse, and export terminological data, thereby promoting knowledge dissemination and linguistic inclusivity.

This multilingual termbase is a global resource to equip people working to protect those at risk of sexual exploitation, abuse or harm to make PSEA (protection against sexual exploitation and abuse) communication more accurate, consistent and appropriate to their context. With the right words to talk about sensitive or traumatic issues, aid organizations can better ensure that people, especially marginalized people, are being listened to and receive the support they need.

In this context, we are currently planning the future steps in the development of this research that will focus on enhancing the database by improving the input and validation processes for new terms, incorporating user feedback to iteratively improve the interface, and experimenting with adaptable interfaces for mobile devices. This includes developing user-friendly interfaces for contributors to submit new terms and definitions, as well as implementing robust validation mechanisms to ensure accuracy and consistency of the added data. Integration of machine learning techniques could aid in automating the validation process, improving efficiency and scalability. Conducting a comprehensive user study will be crucial to gather feedback and insights for enhancing the usability and effectiveness of the web application interface. We will also plan to evaluate the usability and accessibility of the web application in challenging situations, such as limited screen size and varying network conditions. This would also include scenarios where internet connectivity may be unreliable or unavailable which means developing mechanisms to store essential data locally on users' devices, allowing them to access and interact with the terminology database even when offline. These efforts aim to further enhance accessibility, usability, and inclusivity, ultimately contributing to the goal of facilitating cross-cultural communication and knowledge sharing.

¹³ <https://iate.europa.eu/>

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